

ROLE OF REMOTE SENSING DATA IN ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH. DESERTIFICATION AND ITS EXPLORATION USING REMOTE SENSING METHODS

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Over the past 30 years, satellite remote sensing (SRS) has demonstrated high efficiency in informing about biodiversity and ecosystems and determining anthropogenic pressure on landscape, regional, ecosystem, continental and global spatial scales.

Regional and global land surface products derived from data from long-duration satellite missions such as Landsat, the Terra and Aqua Earth Observing System satellites, and the Polar-orbiting Operational Environmental Satellite (POES) series are widely available and offer relatively inexpensive and proven means of obtaining data on various types of geospatial information for large areas that are constantly updated. Commercial systems with very high spatial resolution above 5 m have provided new opportunities for ecosystem mapping.

One of the most significant environmental threats to humanity today is desertification. Desertification is a complex concept that includes a set of degradation processes within the upper soil layer. Desertification is land degradation in semi-arid and arid regions of the globe caused by human activity (anthropogenic causes) and natural factors and processes.

The presence of arid landscapes is the norm for many regions of the Earth, where certain climatic, landscape and geological conditions have formed: high average daily and average annual temperature, low rainfall and, accordingly, low density of vegetation or its complete absence, lack of fertile soils, etc.

Desertification as a process of dynamic change of the Earth's surface over large areas is the subject of many studies using remote sensing data. Complex studies of processes using remote sensing data require the combination of many types of data and the involvement of several processing methods.

Keywords: Desertification, Remote Sensing Data, Ecological modelling

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